

Original Article

AQUIFER CHARACTERIZATION STUDIES OF THE GROUNDWATER POTENTIAL OF GRA KEFFI AND ITS ENVIRONS

**¹Modibbo M.A, ¹Eya A.I and ²Yahaya M*

¹Department of Geology and Mining, Nasarawa State University, Keffi NSUK

²Department of Geological Technology, Isa Mustapha Agwai Polytechnic, Lafia IMAP
DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20796401>

Abstract: This study presents a geoelectrical investigation of the groundwater potential in GRA Keffi and its environs, North Central Nigeria, using Vertical Electrical Sounding (VES) techniques. A total of 20 points were selected from over 120 borehole locations across the area, with data acquired using the Schlumberger array and processed through Win Resist and Surfer 13 software. The results reveal aquifer thicknesses ranging from 5 to 28 m, resistivity values between 90 and 150 Ω m, and piezometric levels between 300 and 314 m, indicating that the aquifers are predominantly hosted in weathered and fractured basement rocks. The depth to fresh basement ranges from 52 to 88 m, while the basement resistivity values span 600-4600 Ω m, reflecting the dominance of crystalline lithologies such as gneiss and granitic gneiss as observed from field observations and megascopic studies. The overburden thicknesses vary between 5.5 and 19.5 m, and the water table levels observed from hand-dug wells range from 1.31 to 3.07 m, suggesting a shallow aquifer system with moderate to high groundwater potential. The study concludes that aquifer occurrence and productivity in the area are strongly influenced by lithological and structural controls, and it provides critical baseline data for sustainable groundwater development and management in crystalline basement terrains.

Keywords: Aquifers, Vertical Electric Resistivity (VES), and Groundwater Potential

1.1 INTRODUCTION

The study of groundwater is essential to humans, and it cannot be overemphasized. In Nigeria today, approximately 60% of its population have their only source of potable hygienic water from groundwater (Omole, 2013). Over the years, Keffi Local Government Area has been on supply of pipe borne water from the Mada waterworks established in 1997, situated within the River Mada catchment in Akwanga Local Government Area. Population growth has exceeded the capacity of the existing water infrastructure, which has prompted residents to seek alternative water sources.

Groundwater resources comprise approximately 95% of the earth's freshwater (Das et al., 2018). It occurs below the water table, occupying the spaces between grains in bodies of sediments and clastic sedimentary rocks,

Original Article

basement rocks, cracks, and crevices of rock (Diary and Lanja, 2016). Mukherjee (2012) opines that the exploration of groundwater in hard rock terrains is challenging because of the complex nature of its occurrence, storage, and distribution, which are influenced by various geological factors. Similar studies have highlighted that aquifer, which are porous and permeable in geologic formations, are the most prolific water sources in basement terrains (Todd and Mays, 2005). A similar assertion was made by Ariyo and Adeyemi (2009), they noted that groundwater in basement complex terrains is highly localized and confined to weathered and fractured zones.

The geoelectrical succession in Nigeria Precambrian crystalline basement terrains typically comprises three distinct layers: a thin (0–2 m) and highly resistive topsoil 100–4,000 Ωm), a more conductive weathered bedrock (10–200 Ωm with a thickness of less than 50 m), and a highly resistive crystalline bedrock (>1,000 Ωm) (Olayinka et al., 2000). To evaluate these geoelectrical parameters and delineate potential aquifers for groundwater exploration, this study employs the VES method within the Keffi area and its environment.

The study area, which includes rapidly developing communities namely: Angwan Jema'a, Angwan Sokotawa, Angwan Jaba, and parts of Dadin Kowa and High Court, is experiencing significant population growth. Therefore, this research aims to contribute new knowledge to existing groundwater studies and provide essential data for sustainable water resource management in a rapidly increasing region

Figure 1. Keffi GRA and the environment Source: (Extracted from Google Earth)

1.2 MATERIALS AND METHOD

This study adopted the vertical electrical sounding (VES) technique to investigate the subsurface geology. The survey was conducted at 20 strategically distributed VES points using an ABEM SAS 1000 resistivity meter with the Schlumberger array configuration. A maximum current electrode spacing (AB/2) of 100 m was used to ensure sufficient penetration depth. The acquired resistivity data were subsequently processed and analyzed using Win

Original Article

Resist software for a one dimensional inversion, while Surfer 13 software was used to generate final plots and spatial maps of the geoelectrical parameters.

The geology of the area was delineated through a combination of field observations (megascopic studies) and a comprehensive desk study of existing literature (Anudu et al., 2012; Goki et al., 2022; and Obrike et al., 2023) to complement the geophysical data. Additionally, the water table depth was measured from 20 hand dug wells that were spatially distributed throughout the study area, providing crucial hydrogeological reference data. Figure 3 shows the location of the VES points and the wells.

1.2.2 Geology of the study area

Keffi is situated within the Lower Paleozoic Precambrian crystalline basement complex of North Central Nigeria (Anudu et al., 2012). This region is primarily composed of Precambrian migmatitic gneisses, gneisses, and Lower Paleozoic Older Granites, with minor schist, pegmatite, and quartz veins. The underlying geology of the Keffi GRA area is covered majorly by the gneiss, which gradually transitions into granitic gneiss toward the northern part of the study area as shown in Figure 2. This lithological context reveals that the local groundwater system is recharged through the crystalline rocks' weathered and fractured zones, a mechanism common to most basement terrains (Anudu et al., 2012).

Figure 2. Geology of the Keffi GRA and its environment.

1.3 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The data from the 20 VES points were processed using Win Resist software. The analysis involved plotting clear resistivity (Ωm) against depth to produce geoelectric sounding curves. These curves, as shown in Figure 3, were categorized into four main types, with the following distribution: HA (5), QH (4), AA (4), and KH (7).

Original Article

Figure 3. VES point map of the study area

Figure 4. KH Curve (L GRA VES 1)

Figure 5. QH Curve (U GRA VES 1)

Original Article

Figure 6. H A Curve (ANG. JAM VES 1)

Figure .7. KH Curve (ANG JAB VES 1)

Figure 8. KH Curve (H COURT VES 1)

Figure 9. Curve (D KOWA VES 1)

Original Article

Figure.10. AA Curve (U SOK VES 2)

Table 1. Summary of qualitative VES interpretation from the quantitative result carried out at Keffi G.R.A and its environment.

S/ N	Noting	Easting	Elevation (m)	Piezometric level (m)	Aquifer thickness (m)	Aquifer Resistivity (Ωm)	Basement Resistivity Ωm)	Depth to Basement (m)	Overburden Thickness (m)
1	7.8982	8.982	300	282	21	174	389	70	18
2	7.8982	8.8547	310	292	20	127	2714	82	18
3	7.8875	8.8557	320	305	10	342	2084	58	5
4	7.8807	8.8535	320	305	13	79	755	45	10
5	7.8941	8.8564	300	286	12	85	1600	50	14
6	7.8937	8.8578	310	300	6	157	4130	65	10
7	7.893	8.8512	310	300	7.5	253	4368	50	10
8	7.9881	8.8528	290	290	14	188	1783	80	20
9	7.8992	8.8542	320	310	8	442	3517	90	10
10	8.8982	8.853	310	290	28	170	3663	90	20
11	7.9072	8.863	300	285	15	125	980	70	15
12	7.9064	8.8585	330	315	12	146	535	55	15
13	7.9085	8.9702	310	303	13	322	1025	80	7
14	7.8925	8.894	310	303	19	121	3076	85	7
15	7.8856	8.8569	300	290	10	157	1362	60	10
16	7.8925	8.8494	300	297	13	103	1082	60	7
17	7.8567	8.8856	300	295	4	313	1205	50	5
18	7.8991	8.8717	310	300	12	138	3630	50	10
19	7.8929	8.8616	310	295	31	116	762	80	15
20	7.8891	8.8539	300	295	4	347	1130	50	15

Original Article

Table 2. Curve characteristics with frequency and percentage

S/N	Location	Curve Types	Curve Characteristics	Curve Frequency	Percentage of curve types
1	Lower GRA	KH	$\rho_1 < \rho_2 > \rho_3 < \rho_4$	7	31.60
2	„	HA	$\rho_1 > \rho_2 < \rho_3 > \rho_4$	5	26.30
3	„	HA	$\rho_1 > \rho_2 < \rho_3 > \rho_4$	5	26.30
4	„	KH	$\rho_1 < \rho_2 > \rho_3 < \rho_4$	7	31.60
5	Upper GRA	QH	$\rho_1 > \rho_2 > \rho_3 < \rho_4$	4	21.05
6	„	QH	$\rho_1 > \rho_2 > \rho_3 < \rho_4$	4	21.05
7	„	QH	$\rho_1 > \rho_2 > \rho_3 < \rho_4$	4	21.05
8	„	QH	$\rho_1 > \rho_2 > \rho_3 < \rho_4$	4	21.05
9	„	HA	$\rho_1 > \rho_2 < \rho_3 < \rho_4$	5	26.30
10	„	AA	$\rho_1 < \rho_2 < \rho_3 < \rho_4$	4	21.05
11	Angwan Jaba	HA	$\rho_1 > \rho_2 < \rho_3 < \rho_4$	5	26.30
12	„	HA	$\rho_1 > \rho_2 < \rho_3 > \rho_4$	5	26.30
13	„	KH	$\rho_1 < \rho_2 > \rho_3 < \rho_4$	7	31.60
14	„	AA	$\rho_1 < \rho_2 < \rho_3 < \rho_4$	4	21.05
15	„	KH	$\rho_1 < \rho_2 > \rho_3 < \rho_4$	7	31.60
16	High Court	KH	$\rho_1 < \rho_2 > \rho_3 < \rho_4$	7	31.60
17	„	KH	$\rho_1 < \rho_2 > \rho_3 < \rho_4$	7	31.60
18	Dadin Kowa	KH	$\rho_1 < \rho_2 > \rho_3 < \rho_4$	7	31.60
19	Angwan Sokotawa	AA	$\rho_1 < \rho_2 < \rho_3 < \rho_4$	4	21.05
20	„	AA	$\rho_1 < \rho_2 < \rho_3 < \rho_4$	4	21.05

Table 3. Summary of the characteristics of the curves with their frequency and percentage

S/N	Curve Types	Curve Frequency	Curve Characteristics	%of Curve Types
1	KH	7	$\rho_1 < \rho_2 > \rho_3 < \rho_4$	35
2	HA	5	$\rho_1 > \rho_2 < \rho_3 > \rho_4$	25
3	QH	4	$\rho_1 > \rho_2 > \rho_3 < \rho_4$	20
4	AA	4	$\rho_1 > \rho_2 > \rho_3 < \rho_4$	20
Total		20		100

Original Article

1.3.1 Piezometric level

The piezometric level of the study area (Figure 11) ranges from 284 to 314 m. From the piezometric map, portions with gray color have the lowest values, ranging from 284 to 288 m. Areas with green color have moderate piezometric values ranging from 288 to 299 m, whereas red color has high piezometric values ranging from 300 to 314 m. This implies that areas with low to moderate piezometric values (gray and green), trending northwest, northeast, west, and north, and in the central region, are toward streams, which serve as convergence zones for surface and groundwater flow, whereas areas with high piezometric values toward the south, southeast, and west, and in part of the north, form ridges and divergence zones for surface and groundwater flow.

Figure 11. Piezometric analysis of Keffi GRA and its environment.

1.3.2 True aquifer thickness

The aquifer thickness fractured basement varies between 5 and 28 m (Table 1). The aquifer units in the study area are mostly found in the weathered and fractured basement or layer. In the contour map of the aquifer thickness as shown in figure 12 indicated that the gray color represents thick aquifer ranges from 5-8 m and has low yield and groundwater potential, the green color represents moderate yield and aquifer thickness of 8-15 m with moderate groundwater potential, and the yellow red color represents a thicker aquifer unit between 15 and 28 m with good groundwater potential.

In addition, the static water level and depth of some of the hand dug wells were measured in location, revealing that the depth ranges from 8 to 12 m, while the static water level ranges from 5 to 9 m occurring mostly within the gneiss with little variation in the granitic gneiss. The result implies that the former has greater water potential than the latter.

Original Article

Figure 12. True aquifer thickness of Keffi GRA and environment.

1.3.3 True aquifer resistivity

The true aquifer resistivity reveals the observed resistivity values of the true aquifer (weathered or fractured basement). Thus, the observed thickness of the aquifer (weathered basement or fractured basement) plays an important role in identifying or zoning groundwater potential in the basement complex terrain (Olatokunbo and Akintorinwa, 2016). The resistivity of the aquiferous layer ranges from 70-370 Ωm in the study area. This reveals the heterogeneous variation in the composition of the weathered or fractured basement layer from sandy clay, laterite, lateritic clay, weathered and fractured granitic gneiss and schist within underlain the area.

The classification of the groundwater potential of the aquifer units based on the resistivity yellow color (Figure 12) implies that areas with resistivity ranging from 90-150 Ωm are zones with optimum weathered and good groundwater potential. These areas are underlain by high weathered granitic gneiss. The green color represents moderate aquifer resistivity regions and depicts moderate aquifer conditions with values 170-310 Ωm while zones with resistivity values between 220 Ωm -370 Ωm possess little aquifer conditions and potential.

Original Article

Figure 13. True aquifer resistivity of Keffi GRA and environment.

1.3.4 Basement resistivity

The basement resistivity in the study area ranges from 600-4600 Ωm (Table 1). This reveals that the resistivity in the study area is not less than 600 Ωm (Figure 14). From the map, the green color dominant in the area reveals a low moderate basement resistivity value of 600 -3600 Ωm while brown-red and black colors with values 3800-4600 Ωm represents high basement value in the area. This reveals that there is little difference in the underlain rocks.

Figure 14. Basement resistivity of the Keffi GRA and its environment.

Original Article

1.3.5 Depth to Fresh Basement

The depth to fresh basement of the study area reveals the thicknesses of each of the layers encountered at the top of the fresh basement beneath the sounding stations (Ojo, 2015). These include the topsoil, laterite, weathered basement, and fractured basement. The depth to the fresh basement ranges from 48 to 88 m (Table 1).

In the contour map of depth to fresh basement (Figure 14), the gray color represents low thickness (48-52m), less percentage of clay, and good degree of porosity and permeability, and the green color represents a thickness ranging from 52-70m, which is represented with green yellow, these colors represents zones with medium basement thickness, while the red color shows areas with high thickness of 72-88m are groundwater receptacle and correspond to the basement depression location. Hence, the study area has moderate high groundwater potential.

Figure 15. Depth to fresh basement of Keffi G.R.A and environment.

1.3.6 Overburden thickness

The overburden thickness of the study (Figure 15) varied from 5.5-19.5m. The depth is composed of topsoil (clayed and weathering materials) and laterite (clay sand, transported weathering materials). It also showed that some probe points can support hand-dug wells (low yield or seasonal wells) and low to high engineering structures due to the thin nature of the clayey overburden (<4m) with relatively high resistivity values in the study area.

Figure 16 reveals that a high overburden thickness is observed. The yellow color represents a low overburden thickness of 5.5-8.5m depth, and the green color indicates a moderate thickness range from 9-16.5m while highest overburden thickness is observed and is showed with red color with thickness of 17-19.5m. The overburden contains sufficient clay material materials, therefore making the hand-dug wells have low yield and moderate when the groundwater saturation is high raining season). This is also applicable to the hand pump, borehole, and hand dug wells in the area.

Original Article

Figure 16. Overburden thickness of Keffi GRA and environment.

1.3.7 Water Table

The water table, which is inversely proportional to an area's groundwater potential serves as the boundary between the aeration and saturation zones (Lionel et al., 2023). Thus, when rain seeps into the groundwater level, it percolates through the gaps or openings of soil and rock fractures, accumulating underground, and the surface is referred to as the water table. The hydraulic head within the study area was classified based on the observed groundwater levels (Figure 7). This classification includes five categories: very high water table (1.31–1.67 m), high (1.68–2.02 m), moderate (2.03–2.37 m), low (2.38–2.72 m), and very low (2.73–3.07 m). Therefore, the study area has an efficient groundwater recharge that is primarily derived from rainfall and the available conducive groundwater percolation and storage enabling systems.

Original Article

Figure 17. Water table of Keffi GRA and Environs

1.4. Hydrogeological Implications

The VES survey results provide valuable insights into the study area's hydrogeological properties. The shallow water table (1.31-1.67m) indicates that the area is potentially prone to groundwater contamination, emphasizing the need for proper waste management and pollution control measures.

The aquifer thickness (5-8m piezometric levels (300-314m) indicate a moderate to good aquifer system, which can support the development of sustainable groundwater. However, to ensure optimal groundwater extraction, the variability in aquifer thickness and piezometric levels may require careful planning and management.

1.4.1 Aquifer Properties

The aquifer resistivity values (90-150 ohm-m) suggest that the aquifer material is likely composed of fractured rock formations, which can exhibit good hydraulic conductivity. The moderate resistivity values (170-310 ohm-m) indicate areas of increased water saturation or better aquifer properties, making them potential targets for groundwater development.

1.4.2 Characteristics of the basement and overburden thickness

The observed depth to the basement (52–70 m) and overburden thickness (5.5–19.5 m) indicate a relatively thick overburden. This thick weathered layer is crucial for groundwater storage and can significantly influence recharge and flow dynamics. The high basement resistivity values (600–3600 Ω m) are indicative of a crystalline bedrock, likely composed of granite or other resistive rocks (Figure 2) acts as a hydraulic barrier to groundwater flow.

1.5 CONCLUSION

This study revealed a comprehensive characterization of the subsurface hydrogeology in the GRA Keffi area. The primary aquiferous zones are situated within the weathered and fractured basement, with thicknesses and resistivity values ranging from 5–28m and 90–150 Ω m, respectively. The combination of a thick overburden (5.5–

Original Article

19.5m) and a deep basement (52–70 m) creates a favorable environment for groundwater storage. This is supported by a recharge mechanism in which the underlying gneiss and granitic gneiss bedrock facilitate infiltration and accumulation. The geo electrical studies reveals four (4) layers KH-(7), HA (5), QH (4), and AA (4). Therefore, the subsurface was generally observed to have litho-logs in the following order: top soil Laterite clay sand weathered basement, weathered/ fractured basement Schist , and fresh basement. The findings provide a crucial scientific basis for effective groundwater exploration and the sustainable management of water resources in this rapidly developing region.

Reference

- Anudu, G. K., Obrike, S. E. and Essien, B. I. (2014). Hydrogeophysical investigation and estimation of groundwater potentials of Lower Paleozoic to Precambrian crystalline basement rocks in the Keffi area of North Central Nigeria using resistivity methods. *Arabian Journal of Geosciences*, DOI-10.1007/s12517-012-0789-x.
- Ariyo, S.O. Adeyemi, G. O. (2009). *Geoelectric investigation of the groundwater potential of Akure South, Southwestern Nigeria*. *Journal of Mining and Geology*, 45(2), 121–134.
- Das B, Pal S, Malik S, Chakraborty R., (2018). Modeling groundwater potential zones off Puruliya districts, West Bengal, India using remote sensing and geographic information system (GIS) techniques *Geol Ecological Landsc* 3:223-237.
- Diary, A. M., & Lanja, F. R. R (2016). Groundwater potential mapping using remote sensing and GIS based, in Halabja city, Kurdistan, Iraq. *Arabian Journal of Geosciences*.
- Goki, M. M., and Musa, U. Ibrahim, A. M. (2022). *Petrology and structural analysis of basement rocks in Keffi, North Central Nigeria* Nigerian Journal of Geoscience Research, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 110–123.
- Lionel, A., & Smith, J. Zhang, Y.(2023). *Hydrogeology and groundwater flow modeling in semi-arid regions* Journal of Hydrology Studies, vol. 14, no. 1, 55–70.
- Mukherjee, P., Singh, C. K. and Mukherjee, S. (2012). Delineation of groundwater potential zones in arid region of India A remote sensing and geographic information system approach *Water Resources Management*, 26(9), 2643–2672.
- Obrike, S. E., and Anudu, G. K. Dewald, L. (2023). *Hydrogeophysical mapping of aquifer zones in crystalline terrains: A case study of Keffi, Nigeria*. *African Journal of Earth Sciences*, vol. 9, no. 1, 33–47.
- Ojo, J.S., Olorunfemi, M.O., Akintorinwa, O.J., Bayode, S., Omosuyi, G.O., Akinluyi, F.O., (2015). GIS Integrated Geomorphological, Geological and Geoelectrical Assessment of the Groundwater Potential of Akure Metropolis, Southwest Nigeria. *J. Geogr. Sci. Technol. Earth Sci. Geotech. Eng.*, 85–101, ISSN: 1792-9040 (print), 1792–9660 (online). Available online: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/288060491>.

Original Article

- Olayinka, A. I and Yaramanci, U (2000). Use of block inversion in the 2D interpretation of plain resistivity data and comparison with smooth inversion. *Journal of Applied Geophysics*, vol. 45, issue 2, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0926-9851\(00\)00019-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0926-9851(00)00019-7), pp. 63-81
- Olorunfemi, M. O., (2007). Groundwater exploration, selection of borehole sites, and optimum drill Depth in the complex basement terrain. *Water Resources Special Publication Series 1 Nigerian Association of Hydrogeologists (NAH), Benin, Benin, Nigeria*
- Mole, D. O., (2013). Sustainable Groundwater Exploitation in Nigeria *Journal of Water Resource and Ocean Science* 2(2): 9, <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.wros.20130202.11> DOI:10.11648/j.wros.20130202.11
- Todd, D. K., & Mays, L. W. (2005). *Groundwater hydrology*, 3rd ed. Wiley, New 636.